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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Projects are not new to the business world. As a matter of fact, project has been with humans' right from the Socratic era, to Egyptian civilization, to Greek civilization and up till the postmodern civilization as it is today. It is pertinent to call to mind that no person, team, group, company or organization set out on a project with the sole intent of ensuring that the project is a failure. In other words the underlying intent of every project is for it to be successful by meeting its set goals and objectives and not for it to fail. History (both in the social and academic realm) is filled examples of projects that have been successful and projects that have failed woefully. In the view of Cynthia West (2014) for instance almost all organizations have experienced projects failure or a project that exceed the time that was allotted for its completion as a result of poor budgeting or even a change in scope as time goes on the execution of the project. This has led to the conception that there are more failed projects than successful ones today. Lewis (2013) holds that on average, roughly 70 percent of project carried out in the IT industry fail attain set objectives and goals.

It is important at this juncture clear the air on the understanding of the concept of “project failure” within the context of this work. In this work a project will be considered as failed when it fails to meet the specified time line, when it is abandoned, when it over budgeted and when it is found defective upon completion. The reason for this clarification is informed by varied understanding of the concept of project failure. For example some people may not consider a change in scope or delay in time as failure while some will consider this as such.

This work takes a look at why projects should not fail by paying attention to critical success factors in project management. The research is carried out among ICT companies in Cyberjaya, Malaysia. The high number of projects that companies within this industry engage in and their high concentration in the specific location of study inform the Choice of this industry and location.

As the maiden phase of this research work, this chapter introduces the research endeavor by trying to create familiarity with the subject matter of study. Consequently, in this chapter the researcher takes a look at stringent topics that touch at the heart of the research such as the background of study, research problem, research objectives, research hypothesis, research questions, methodology and significance of study.

1.2 BACKGROUND OF STUDY

Irrespective of the type of project, organizing projects could be a very tricky task. This even becomes worse when project managers are under pressure to deliver successful outcome within a specific time frame. Despite the plethora of latest tools that being used today in the field of project management the situation does not seem to have changed significantly. As a matter of fact many have argued that the rate of failure today is just about the same as it was when the keeping of records stated to count. It is also a fact that a large number of projects often spell failure before they ever get started. The burning question has to be: why do these bullheaded statistics refuse to improve?

In Malaysia for instance there has been an increasing awareness of the transformational opportunities offered by information and communication technology (ICT) in the area of improving productivity, growth, competitiveness, poverty reduction and wealth creation. As a matter of fact, ICT was enlisted a major catalyst for economic growth during the implementation of the economic transformation program (ETP) which is concentrated on an all-encompassing and sustainable ingenuity that will change Malaysia into a nation of high income latest, by the year 2020. Nevertheless, according to Nawari et al (2013), there are still a number peculiar challenges that are still being faced in the execution of ICT projects resulting in low success rates to some degree.

According to Charvat (2013), management can be defined as a group of tools techniques and knowledge that, help to see to the actualization of the primary project constraints of cost time and scope. However, based on literature, about 52. Percent of projects for prey to late completion and cost issues, and 31.1 percent failed to meet the scope that was outlined at the initiation of the project (Clancy, 2008). There is no doubt that the advancement in technology and knowledge has made project management more complex than it was many years ago specifically because projects today have incorporated the latest advances. Currently, a lot of companies' concentration on project management, in a bid to achieving project objectives. It is very important when it comes to managerial processes due to the presence of tools that give managers a good opportunity to succeed in the attainment of set goals and objectives. It is possible for a project manager to embark on a reform of almost everything from a project management perspective, however the project can still fail when assessed against its success criteria. There are different tools and techniques that can be used by project managers to carry out their duties efficiently.

Some of these include, charts, macro and micro approach to cost estimation and techniques that help in the scheduling of resources to mention but a view. Utilizing these tools and techniques in the right manner can be used to channel the project towards success

Today, there is a lot of emphasis on an integrated project management process which looks into channeling all projects efforts to the organization's strategic plan while at the same time, annexing adequate control for the use of project management tools and techniques as well as all necessary skills needed to achieve the completion of a project successfully (Calney, 2008).

Why projects should not fail?

The business world today is characterized with groundbreaking developments in almost every sphere of life. The break through and developments in the field of information and communication technology has been one of the greatest leading to the digitalization and automation of almost everything that is done in the business world today. This level of development and advancement has been incorporated into the field of project management with a variety of tools, techniques and training now being provided to project managers not just to aid them in their duties as project managers but to ultimately ensure that project set goals and objects are met within specified time frame and cost allocation.

Furthermore, several researches have been carried out within the field of project management focusing on "why projects failed" little attention has however been given to examine "projects should not fail". With the level of awareness, advancement, guidelines, available tools and studies done in project management projects are not expected to fail if project managers adhere strictly to the aforementioned elements be adhered to. Hence, the critical success factors that ensure projects don't fail shall be examined.

1.3 RESEARCH PROBLEM

It no news that many projects have failed, are failing, and may continue to fail across the globe if adequate measures are not taken by organizations. As a matter fact, many organizations lose millions due to the failure of projects today. This persisting challenge has led many project management professionals to attempt to identify the critical factors necessary to produce a successful project management outcome. The situation is such that having realized the vital role of project management organizations across the globe are beginning to invest big into it. As these huger investments go in, it is only logical to expect that there will be more successful projects recorded. However, the reverse has been the case as the number of failed projects in business organizations and in the business world today is still alarming.

According to Cranfield (2014), it seems that as projects become more complex and multifaceted, so also the reasons for their failure become ever more sophisticated and multidimensional. In another research conducted by Standish group (2007), they found out that information and communication technology (ICT) projects fail at a higher rate when compared to projects in other industries. In the same vein, Kappelman et al (2006) also opined that the high number of incomplete and failed information and communication technology projects have negative impacts on organizational performance. It based in this that the quest to investigate into those vital factors (apart from the availability of funds) that are crucial to the execution and c\completion of projects within the terrain of project management.

1.4 RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

1. To identify and understand the factors that aid project success in organizations
2. To explore different measures to prevent and avoid project failure in organizations
3. To recommend possible strategies that could be implemented to aid project success in organizations

1.5 RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What are the essential factors needed to achieve success in project management organizations?
2. What are the measures taken by ICT organizations that are used to prevent and avoid project failures?
3. Which techniques/methods that aid project management success in organizations?

1.6 HYPOTHESIS

HO: There is no significant relationship between project success and clear goals and objectives.

H1: There is a positive relationship between project success and clear goals and objectives.

HO: There is no significant relationship between project success and planning.

H2 There is a positive relationship between project success and planning.

HO: There is no significant relationship between project success and clear project scope.

H3: There is a positive relationship between project success and clear project scope.

H0: There is no significant relationship between project success and effective communication.

H4: There is a positive relationship between project success and effective communication.

1.7 SIGNIFICANCE OF STUDY

The focal point of this academic piece dwells on an examination of the causes of project failures. As earlier mentioned, the failure of projects is no longer alien to our business world today. As a matter of fact, some as normal and unavoidable is now conceiving project failure. This has led to several studies in the field of project management so as to come up with better and impeccable techniques to best manage progress or at least reduce the chances of project failure to its utmost minimum. Consequently, this study will not only help to identify those factors that cause project failure (with reference to earlier researches) but also come up with possible measures to mitigate them so as to enhance the actualization of organizational set goals and objectives as it pertain the management of projects within the context of study and by extension on a global scale. This will help organizations to better manage projects and increases success rates in the implementation of their various projects. Apart from helping organizations to avoid project failure, this work also contributes to the epistemological edifice of project management as a discipline and profession of its own right. From the above highlighted, the significance of this study can out lines as follows:

- i. Helps Project managers identify and work towards critical success factors in project management
- ii. Serves as a platform for organizations to better manage their projects and thus increase success rates in the execution of projects.
- iii. Exposes possible drawbacks that may lead to project failure and guides managers on how to best approach them
- iv. This study will serve as a point of reference for future researchers who wish conduct further study in this area of study.

1.8 SCOPE OF THE STUDY

The content scope comprises of poor Planning and estimation, poor implementation, incompetent human factor and change as factors that cause project failure. The review of literature as well as survey therefore focuses on the above.

1.9 THESIS ORGANIZATION

The entire work can consist of five major phases designated as chapters. The first chapter is the introduction and introduces the entire research, stating the background, research objectives, research questions as well as the scope and the limitation of this work. The introduction also takes a step further by creating familiarity with the location and industry where the research is conducted.

The second chapter dwells on a literature review on issues surrounding the subject for these researches specifically project management, project failures, project success and critical project management success factors.

The third chapter elaborates on the various techniques and methods adopted in gathering data that would be analyzed in the succeeding chapter. It further explained analytical tools that will be used to analyze the collected data.

The fourth chapter deals with a proper analysis of the data gathered and the findings from the data. Here, the various findings of the research are analyzed and deduced from collected data.

The fifth and final chapter draws the Curtin on the entire work by drawing the implication of study from the findings in the pen-ultimate chapter and also wrapping up the research endeavor with a recommendation and conclusion based on the findings from the study.

2.0 Dissertation outline

This analysis comprises of five sections. In the first chapter, the point of the study and study's Noteworthiness is unmistakably represented. In second section (chapter two), the basic audit Of key hypotheses with research crevices are portrayed. In third section (chapter three), the Research methodology used in this study was which include the group of utilized strategies , Research design, sampling method, exploration plan, inspecting strategy, information Accumulation and information examination techniques. In the fourth chapter, Demographic Testing, unwavering quality examination, connection examination and theory testing will be Researched. At last, in section five (chapter five), conclusion to study, suggestions and Constraints of study will be portrayed. For this situation, the five sections as per figure 1-1 are:

Figure 1-1: Dissertation Outline

CHAPTER TWO

LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 UNDERSTANDING PROJECTS

It is an undisputed fact that humans have carried out projects right from the earliest days of organized human activities. Andrew (2004) for instance, argued that the pre-historic hunting parties of early could be considered as a form of project because their endeavor was directed at a specific goal, which was to food or meat for the larger community. A few Centuries after this, the world also witnessed construction of pyramids in Egypt as well as the construction of the great wall of China which are all projects in every sense or ramification of the word. Although the word can be used in a variety of ways today, a project is generally considered as an organization of people who are dedicated to a specific purpose and objective. Apart from this general conception of projects Rodgers (2014) also argues that projects also generally involve high risk, huge, expensive and unique undertakings that have to be completed within a specific time frame, with specific amount of funds allocated and a specified level of performance expected as the outcome. Fundamentally all projects must necessarily have laid down objectives as well as the necessary resources to execute all the required tasks to meet these objectives.

One of primary distinctive attributes of projects when compared to business operations or an ongoing work is the fact that projects are fundamentally temporary in nature. Projects are not an everyday endeavor or process but have definite state and end dates. This particular point is important in understanding the nature of projects because a large percentage of efforts is often devoted by project managers to ensure that a project is completed and ready at the specified time

and date. As a result of this schedules are created indicating when different tasks are expected to begin and when they expected to end. Depending on the size and nature of the project a project can last for minutes hours, days, weeks, months or years (Davidson, 2009).

Projects are usually embarked on to bring about a particular product or service that was not in existence before. This is why a project is often described as a unique endeavor. A project can only be said to be completed when its set goals and objectives have been accomplished and met. A project can also end in rare cases when it is resolute that the goals and objectives cannot be met or when the service or product is no longer needed.

2.2 WHAT IS PROJECT MANAGEMENT?

In its modern sense, project management began in the early 1950s even though its genesis can be traced back to the 19th century. The driver for project management was businesses realizing the benefits of organizing work around projects and the critical need to communicate and coordinate work across departments and professions (Duncan, 2014). While it is a fact that many individuals may not have formal training in the field of project management, taking a role in a project management team could be an amazing learning opportunity which can boost an individual's career.

In the view of Margaret (2013), project management is a methodical approach to planning and guiding project processes from start to finish. According to the Project Management Institute, the processes are guided through five stages: initiation, planning, executing, controlling, and closing. Project management can be applied to almost any type of project and is widely used to control the complex processes of software development projects. Successful project management has several significant characteristics. To understand the value of project management, it is necessary

to understand the fundamental nature of a project; the core characteristics of project management processes; how success is evaluated, the roles, responsibilities, and activities of a project manager and the expertise required; and the context in which projects are performed (PMI, 2004)

In another view, project management is defined as the science (and art) of organizing the mechanisms of a project, whether the project is development of a new product, the launch of a new service, a marketing campaign, or a wedding. It is important at this juncture to note that a project is not a normal business operation rather it is created once, temporary and specific (MPUG, 2014). As a discipline, what comprises project management varies and is majorly determined by the nature of the project, the role of the project manager and the stage of the project life cycle that the project manager is working on.

As a result of the advent of project management, modern day organizations have adopted a totally new way of doing business which has led to the abandonment of rigid, hierarchical and divided system of labor characteristic of the business world many years ago. This new approach rests on 'projects'; unique, transient endeavor, undertaken to achieve planned objectives, which could be defined in terms of outputs, outcomes or benefits (APM, 2016). According to Anna (2011), project management today works in such a way that it abandons the reliance on pigeonholed workers to conduct single routine tasks in favor of relying on teams of connected experts to work together on holistic projects, focusing their energy on one goal at a time.

2.3 THE BASICS OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT

2.3.1 Defining the Project

In this stage the project manager defines what the project is and what the users hope to achieve by undertaking the project. It is important to also highlight what the project is not at this point so as to ensure that the goals and objectives are very clear to everyone in the project team. This phase also includes a list of project deliverables, the outcome of a specific set of activities. The project manager works with the business benefactors or manager who wants to have the project implemented and other stakeholders — those who have a bestowed interest in the outcome of the project.

2.3.2 Planning the Project

Define all project activities.

Here, the project manager is expected to list all the various tasks and activities, how they are related, how long they will take, and the connection between each task and the deadline. This phase of the project also gives the manager the opportunity to define the relationship between various tasks. The project manager can also set deadlines for sub accomplishments in the project to aid the achievements of overall project aim and objectives.

Define requirements for completing the project.

At this stage the manager is expected to identify the number of manpower and amount (cost) required to execute the project from start to finish. Assumptions as well as risks are also expected to be managed by the project manager at this stage. Project constraints could also be identified at this stage. Constraints typically relate to schedule, resources, budget, and scope. A change in one constraint will typically affect the other constraints. It is usually expected that a change in one constraint has a way of affecting another.

2.3.3 Executing the Project

Here the project manager should know the number of resources and funds available for the execution of the project. The project manager then assigns those resources and allocates budget to various tasks in the project. It is here that the work of the project begins. It is also important that the project manager carries all stakeholders along at this stage especially at the earliest part of the project. This is because it is at this point that primary decisions about the nature of the project are made and mistakes at the earliest stage of a project could be very detrimental to a project if not properly managed.

2.3.4 Controlling the Project

The project manager is in charge of updating the project plans to reflect actual time elapsed for each task. By keeping up with the details of progress, the project manager is able to understand how well the project is progressing overall. The stage of project control is as important that every other phase of the project. This is due to the possibility of derailing from the set goals and objectives of the project due to factors that can be triggered by change which are inevitable in the execution of projects today. It is also vital that the project manager carries other stakeholders along at this stage so as to ensure that the primary goals of the stakeholders and by extension that of the project are met.

2.3.5 Closure of the Project

The project manager and business owner basically carry out this stage. Here, the project manager and business owner pull together the project team and those who have an interest in the outcome of the project (stakeholders) to analyze the final result of the project. In analyzing the final result of the project an evaluation is done by placing the achievement of the results of the projects along side with the aims and objectives of the project at the genesis of the project.

2.4 The Constraint model

From time immemorial, the project constraint model has always recognized three major key constraints namely time, scope and cost. These constraints are usually represented with a triangle, which shows the relationship between the factors, which is always interdependent. Should there arise the need to change any of the factors, a minimum of one or two of the other factors will be affected (Erik, 2003). Within the conventional acceptance of the Triangle Model, "Cost" and "Time" are usually represented as more consistent while scope is often used interchangeably specifically because of the illustration of the triangle or respective projects perception.

2.4.1 Project Time

This has to do with the real time that is required to deliver a particular result. Usually, the time that is needed to produce a particular result is directly related to the number of requirements which are part of the result (scope) in addition to the amount of resources (cost) allocated for the purpose of the project in question. The activities of a project can either be long or short depending on the amount of time available for the project to be completed. It is important to note that the completion of a project requires the completion of different tasks which in-turn is affected by the number of people working on the project, skills level and experience to mention but a few. Time is a very significant factor in project management because it is not within the control of the project manager or stakeholders. In addition to this, failure of a project to meet set deadlines can create adverse and detrimental effects. According to Stephen (2006) one of the primary reasons why people fail to meet timelines in project management is the unavailability of resources.

2.4.2 Project Cost

Project cost can be defined as the approximation of the cost required to completely execute the project from the beginning to the end. All aspects of the project that have a monetary component are made part of the overall cost structure. It will be absolute unwise to embark on a project without carrying out an adequate budget and funding analysis that will span from the start to the finish of the project. In others words it is imperative for both project managers and organizations to have an estimated cost when undertaking a project. Budgets will ensure that project is developed or implemented below a certain cost. Sometimes, project managers have to allocate additional resources in order to meet the deadlines with a penalty of additional project costs. It is important that project management create room for these additional costs in their planning in the entire course of the project execution.

2.4.3 Project Scope

Simply put, scope refers to the functional that make up the deliverables of the project when completed. In order to give the project the best possible chance of success, the scope of a project is usually identified up front. Although there is the possibility of a change in scope during the life span of a project (due to scope creep) it is important to note that the common success measure for the scope aspect of a project is its inherent quality upon delivery. Scope looks at the outcome of the project undertaken. This consists of a list of deliverables, which need to be addressed by the project team. It is vital that a successful and competent project manager is able to manage both the scope of the project and any change in scope, which impacts, time and cost while the projects lasts. Managing scope in special projects can be very tricky and sometimes demanding. In all the entire endeavor of scope management focuses on the collection processes that are used to guarantee the availability of all task needs to complete a project while at the same time, eliminating any work that is outside the project scope (Palmer, 2016). In the scope management

plan, the detail of how the scope will be defined is addressed. The Scope Management Plan contains how the definition, development and verification of the project will be done. It explicitly states the individual or group who is to manage the project's scope as well as the necessary guide for controlling the project scope.

The fundamentally and undisputed nature of the triple constraints triangle is that one cannot be adjusted having an effect on the other two. A change in the scope at the middle of project must necessarily have an effect on the attributes of time and cost in one way or the other. It is always a vital requirement to overcome the challenges related to the project triangle during the project implementation period. Project managers need to understand that the three constraints outlined in the project management triangle can be adjusted (Tutorialpoints, 2013).

2.5 WHY PROJECTS FAIL?

Projects are naturally very fiddly to organize especially when under pressure produce certain deliverables within a specified time with limited resources. As a matter of fact, the various tools being introduced and used in the field of project management today has not reduced the complexity and complicated nature of projects. Some have even argued that the failure rate in project management today is just about the same as from the onset (John, 2014). Many more projects even spell failure before they are started hence, the question why should projects fail or why should they not fail? In an ideal world, every project would be "within budget and schedule. In reality however, this is not the case as project failure is a common phenomenon today. It is very possible for the budget and timeline to be met, however, it is also important ask "did the project deliver the results and quality expected?" It is pertinent that projects are assessed on all three components. Failure to meet any of these components could be regarded as failure as it applies to the project.

2.6 PROJECT SUCCESS FACTORS (Why they should not fail)

In a report published by Standish Chaos (1994), ten important factors were identified to aid successful projects namely, executive management support, clear requirement statement, user involvement competent staff, realistic expectations, ownership, clear vision and objectives. Of the aforementioned ten factors four were identified to contribute more to project success. They include executive management support, user involvement, clear statement of requirement and proper planning.

- a. User involvement: Even when a project is delivered on time and within specified budget, a project can still fail if it does not meet the requirements of the user. Hence it is important that the user is involved in every phase of the project to avoid project failure.
- b. Executive management support: This has the ability to impact the progress and process of any given project in an organization. A project could be highly severely disadvantaged if this is absent.
- c. Clear statement of requirements: This has to do with the primary requirement of a project. Here a base level of requirements is created. It is important that this level of requirement is minimal and achievable so as to mitigate the impact of change on the project. The advantage of this is that project managers will be well prepared to understand and prioritize the needs of subsequent project phases.
- d. Proper planning: Planning is a critical aspect of project management. It is one of the key factors to a successful project. As a matter of fact, it should be one of the first steps to take when embarking on any project endeavor.

2.7 THE EXTENDED TRADITIONAL THEORY OF PROJECT MANAGEMENT SUCCESS

Figure 1-2

Three conceptual thread that runs through a plethora of project management success' definitions are the dimensions of budget, time and specifications (Globerson and Zwikael, 2002, Thomsett, 2003). While this cannot be disputed it is important to note that budget time and specification are not sufficient enough in themselves to measure project management success. Other dimensions such as the satisfaction of the project stakeholders and the quality of project management process also require a great deal of attention since they touch at the heart of project management success (Schwalbe, 2004). Consequently an extensions of the of the tradition triangle in the above model to include the quality of management process as well as stakeholders satisfaction offers the part-way for a more holistic view an appreciation of the project management.

It is also important to point out the strong links that exist between product success and project management success. Although their outcomes are inseparable Pinkerton (2003) argues that the causal relationship between them is weak. For instance a project can be said to be a failure if it goes beyond the allotted time and budget, the resulting product of the project can still be a success if it meets the quality and specifications slated at the beginning of the project (Pinkerton, 2003).

2.8 CAUSES OF PROJECT FAILURE

Projects can fail for many reasons. Common reasons why projects fail include the failure to plan and estimate correctly, failure to see to the implementation of tasks according to plan, failure caused by humans due to their imperfect nature and failure caused by change at any stage within the project.

2.8.1 Planning and Estimation factor

This factor refers to initial cost and schedule estimates are not revised when more information becomes available as a project progresses. Also plans are not used correctly or used to guide the project forward, thus causing the project to fail. As the popular saying goes, 'he who fails to plan plans to fail'. Planning is very central to any project endeavor and it is most important that the right plans and strategies that match the set goals and objectives of the project are put in place.

2.8.2 Implementation factor

Many projects also fail at the level of implementation. Failure at this level can be mostly caused by project scope changes, incorrect use of project methodology, major changes in the requirements and testing, and/or inspections are poorly done. If the project manager and his team do not properly manage this it could lead to not just a delay in the project but also incurring additional project cost and in severe cases a premature end to the project.

2.8.3 Human factor

Although humans are not perfect, the lack of the required skills and knowledge to manage and execute a project on the part of the project manager and other team members could lead to failure or even pre-mature demise of the project. If a manager for instance is not able to apply and put the theories of project management to practice there is every chance for the project to fail. Poor communication within the project team can also be responsible for project failure. According to Coley (2008), the inappropriate use of scheduling methodology and project planning is one of the major causes of project failure. In a research carried out by Martin (2013), projects that faced challenges during their life span and were still successful had project managers who were well knowledgeable and equipped technical skills. On the other hand failed projects showed the project managers only had fair skills. According to the 2002 Standish Report (Wasileski, 2005), the three major factors that impacted negatively on not accomplished projects are lack of user input, incomplete requirements and specifications, and changing requirements and specifications.

2.8.4 Change Factor

Change is an inevitable factor in the in our world today. It is a reality that businesses as well as project managers need to face from time to time. Change is even happening at a faster rate that has never been witnessed before in the history of humanity. Consequently it will be very unrealistic for any project manager not to expect change or make plans to accommodate it. However uncontrolled changes play havoc with a system under development and have caused many project failures. This emphasizes the advantages of shorter timescales and a phased approach to building systems, so that change has less chance to affect development.

Despite the above, change still has to be managed just as every other business factor. It is important the project manager or business embarks on a proper evaluation of the impact of any change in the requirement on projects on cost, time and the possible risk that this exposes the project to. Change Management and its sister discipline of Configuration Management are skills that can be taught. Change is most likely the most complicated area in the execution of the projects.

The challenge that comes with change is such that the project manager may have to review the original requirements and goals partway of the project so as to decide how to proceed, and this may result in changing the scope of your project – or even canceling the project altogether. In an environment that is radiated with constant change, the possible risks in the project as a result of change can be minimized by making timely decisions, considering smaller projects and managing expectations.

Making timely decisions: Be it in the field of project management or in the broader profession of business management, the importance of decision making especially on the part of the project manager cannot be over emphasized at any length. In a situation where the project manager discovers that the project will not be able to deliver its requirements it is very vital that he communicates this to all stakeholder on time so as to avoid sudden demise of the project and to come up with better change management strategies to aid the project. Here the communication skills of the project management are also expected to be put to play so as not to leave any vital issue unaddressed.

Considering smaller projects; According to Stella (2005) it's more difficult to change direction in a large cruise ship than in a tugboat. Hence project management should consider whether a proposed project's scope and delivery timeline are appropriate within your business environment. Delivering projects in smaller pieces is not always appropriate, but it's worth considering when things go sore due to the challenges posed by change. While this position could be considered plausible, it is also important to consider the option of channeling smaller pieces of projects towards a particular end. In other words, rather than delivering projects in smaller pieces managers can look into annexing these smaller pieces towards a common end such that these different smaller pieces of project serve as units of a common end.

Managing expectations: it is important to note that the cancellation of a project is not necessarily an indication of failure. This depends on many factors, including how you manage the involvement of key project stakeholders in the decision-making process. The expectations of project can be multifaceted and a project manager should also be prepared for every possible eventuality. The inevitability of change in the management of projects is another factor that points to the need for managers to manage expectations appropriately.

2.9 AVOIDING THE COMMON PITFALLS

2.9.1 Constituent Alignment

The presence of stakeholders who engage actively in the project makes it possible for successful projects to deliver in huge part. Whether they are executives of particular business units, or those from the top executive management and sponsors, their contribution is vital to the success of project management. It is a clear fact that projects initiative is bound to suffer without adequate support from management. The alignment issue has to do with ensuring that project goals and objectives are in harmony with the basic vision of the organization (Oracle, 2011).

Pitfall Avoidance: The best practice that could be recommended for the above is to ensure that objective and goals are clearly defined and reviewed. It is also pertinent to note that changes and the cancellation of projects could easily become a routine in this type process. Organizations can however try to mitigate this by ensuring the existence of a standardized pattern of communication so as to help all stakeholders involved in the project.

2.9.2 Proactive Risk Management

Of the various aspects of project management, risk management seems to be given the least of attention. In most situations it has been discovered that project management risks are not properly and proactively diagnosed and lessened. According to oracle (2011), the situation is such that even when risk is identified as a crucial part of the execution of projects, less attention is usually given to this. There is a difference between addressing problems proactively and reactively. More often than not projects usually address problems using a reactive approach, which is not the best approach in problem solving. Such reactions to problems can easily lead to an increase in budgets, schedule spillage and even burnout on the part of employees.

Pitfall Avoidance: In order for project managers and organizations to avoid this pit fall organizations need to integrate a risk management system that is proactive for every aspect of the project. A very important aspect of this will be the publication and developments of the organizations plan for the risk management as well as educating all stakeholders on the importance of implementing project management. In addition to this, it is also essential for project managers to ensure that relevant data for risk management is made available to through the use of reports and self-service portals at all times

2.9.3 Performance Measurement

Almost everyone has come across the concept of performance management. While a lot of emphasis is placed on this aspect in general organizational management and project management very little is usually done in this critical aspect of project management. When there is no proper yardstick to measure project performance it will be very difficult to fully monitor the progress of the project and identify those areas where improvements are needed. Due to this it becomes very difficult to identify deficient areas on time so as to come up with remedies or corrective actions to combat relevant issues.

Pitfall Avoidance: In order to address this situation organization can make use of already standardized project performance standards to measure schedule, effort and products when deemed necessary. Earned value management (EVM) plays an important role here and can even be implemented in small projects.

2.9.4 Project scope definition and management

When the scope of a project is not clearly written and specified and there is pressure of the project to be executed on time without a proper definition, such a project is definitely heading for collapse. This as described by Oracle (2011) is one of the classic cases of project failure waiting to happen. It may sound trite, yet project scope must be clear, concise, and unambiguous. It must be clearly and commonly understood by project stakeholders, team members, and executives alike.

Pitfall Avoidance: The recommended approach is to ensure that a proper review of the project scope is done with the community of users and obtain a 100 percent approval on what is about to be initiated or delivered in the project. (Oracle, 2011). To gain the commitment of all project

stakeholders it is essential that they have a clear understanding of the scope of the project. An agreement should be obtained on those things that are within scope and those that are out scope. It will not also be out of place to establish a change procedure that is formal. . Designing the “perfect” solution with a very broad scope frequently leads to intricate, multi-year projects with complex interdependencies. It is also important that project managers ensure that scope is limited to things that are achievable through well-defined efforts. With tighter project scope, the organization can do a better job of monitoring progress and controlling outcomes. For complex, expensive projects containing many unknowns and volatile risks, institute a scope investigation phase in advance of project approval and execution (Oracle, 2011). The scope investigation can take the form of a pilot, a proof-of-concept research paper, a benchmarking analysis of similar projects, or a simulation. Irrespective of the chosen approach, the method of using a pre-project to define scope is expected to bring the much-needed clarity to the primary project and improve the chances of its success.

2.9.5 Critical Project Communication

It is vital for project managers and stakeholders to be aware of project progress and challenges at every stage. Unfortunately, stakeholders are often informed of critical issues at a stage when the impact on costs, timelines and scope are significant or irreversible (Oracle, 2011). Inadequate communication of project status and issues is a function of stakeholder needs and expectations not being managed appropriately. Obviously, resolving the issues takes time away from planned project activities. This issue will affect any part of the project.

Pitfall Avoidance: First and foremost, create a communications management plan. This should be comprised of two parts: project communications and stakeholder communications (Oracle, 2011). These activities must be initiated at project kickoff, with particular effort put into performing a stakeholder analysis to identify expectations and communication needs. Be prepared to deliver project status and updates through more than one information delivery vehicle in order to accommodate the diverse needs of stakeholders.

2.9.6 Methodology Usage

The importance of methodologies in aiding successful projects has not been given much attention. The choice of a methodology, whether standardized or organization-specific, is secondary to its usage and adherence during project execution (Oracle, 2011). Enforcement of the chosen methodology is vital. This task is made easier via automation and tools that incorporate project workflow into the overall project execution lifecycle.

Table of References

Authors	Year	Methods	Variables	Main concept
Leon A. Kappelman, Robert McKeeman, and Lixuan Zhang	2006	Survey	Lack of top management support, Weak project manager, No stakeholder involvement and/or participation, Weak commitment of project team, Team members lack requisite knowledge and/or skills, Subject matter experts are overscheduled	Signs of Project Failure
Bikram Pal Kaur and Dr.Himanshu Aggrawal	2013	Review	Information System, Critical Success factor, Critical failure factor, IS,	Project Failure Factors

			organization	
Kjetil Holgeid and Mark Thompson	2013	Survey	Project Failure, Project Success, Emergent, Causal Agency, Emergent Perspective	Causes of Large Project Failure
PMBOK® Guide	2004	Review	A project, Project management, Project success, A project management plan	Water Management
Henk Harmsen Rutger Kramer Laurents Sesink Joris van Zunder	2004	Book	Project management	Introducing Project management
Peter Henderson	2006	Modeling	Size, quality, cost, schedule, complexity	IT project Failure
Sauer, C and C. Cuthbertson,	2004	Survey	Performance management, project performance, project variance	IT projects
Xia, W and G. Lee (2004)	2004	Survey	Structural Organizational Complexity Structural IT Complexity Dynamic Organizational Complexity and Dynamic IT Complexity	Project Complexity
Humphrey, W.S	2013	Survey	Quality, cost, schedule, complexity	Failure of big projects
Nilofur Abbasi, Iqra Wajid , Zahra Iqbal and Fareeha Zafar	2014	Case study	Scope creep, Communication gap, Project visibility	Project failure
Guru Prakash Prabhakar	2010	Review	Project success, project manager,	Factors that impact project

			organization, external environment	success
Saadé, R. G., Dong, H., & Wan, H.	2015	Survey	communication, client, and end-user commitment	Project Manager Success
Wright, G. P., and Adviser-Gottwald, W. D	2013	Survey	Communication, leadership, Teamwork, top management	Project Success
Serrador, P., & Pinto, J. K	2015	Survey	perceived quality of the vision/goals of the project, project complexity, and project team experience	Project success
Sage, D., Dainty, A., and Brookes, N	2014	Review	positivism, structural Marxism, interpretivism and actor-network theory	Project failure/Success
Müller, R., & Turner, R	2007	Survey	project type, industry sector and traits of the project manager	Project Success factors
Müller, R., & Turner, R	2012	Survey	Critical success factors, Project management, Project success, Success measures	Project Success factors
Keil, M., Lee, H. K., & Deng, T.	2013	Survey	Communication, scope, cost, time management	Project success
Gemünden, H. G	2015	Survey	Project success, knowledge sharing, and special issues	Success Factors
Bikram Pal Kaur and Dr.Himanshu Aggrawal	2013	Review	Information System, Critical Success factor, Critical failure factor, IS, organization	Project Failure Factors

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.0 INTRODUCTION

This section of the research methods adopted and utilized in this study. These include the procedure used for data collection, procedures for sampling as well as the techniques and methods of data collection. It also takes a step further to elaborate on how the research was conducted with special focus on how available resources were put to maximum use by the researcher.

The main focus of this research as stated and discussed in preceding chapters is to examine why projects should not fail with a special focus on information and communication technology (ICT) companies in Cyberjaya, Malaysia. Therefore in this chapter, the researcher tried to explain the significance of methodologies, methodological assumptions, approaches as well as the limitations inherent in the research. The statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) was used as the primary tool for data analysis running tests such descriptive analysis reliability analysis, linear regression, correlation and hierarchical regression to mention but a few. The importance of this lies in the fact that the result extracted from the methodology is the main source for the findings and interpretations of the research. Should the wrong methodology be selected, the entire result and findings of the research could be affected, hence the significance of this chapter in the entire course of this research.

The theory adopted in this research is an extension of the traditional theory, which is based on the dimensions of dimensions of budget, time and specifications. In the extension of this theory the traditional triangle was extended to include the quality of management process as well as stakeholders satisfaction offers the partway for a more holistic view an appreciation of the project management.

3.1 RESEARCH APPROACH

3.1.1 Primary Data

The term primary source or primary data is used in quite a number of disciplines to describe source materials that are closed to an idea, person, and information or object that is being studied (University of Maryland Library guide, 2010). Primary data are information collected by the researcher himself. Many methods can be used in primary data collection. They include, questionnaires, interviews, observation, case study and focus groups to mention but a few. Within the context of this work, primary data utilized by the researcher was a questionnaire, which was prepared and tested before distributed to respondents to elicit their response on various issues pondering on the subject matter of, discuss.

The importance of primary data to this research cannot overemphasize. This is because it provides original and relevant data to the topic of this research to a very high degree of accuracy. The Reliability level of primary data is also very high because they were collected directly from those involved in the subject matter of study.

3.2 QUANTITATIVE METHOD

The functional paradigm, which is popularly known as the positivist paradigm, informs the quantitative mode of investigation as it is centered on that social reality has an objective ontological structure and that individuals are responding agents are responding agents to this environment. According to Smith (2008), quantitative research has to do with the counting and measurement of events and carrying out statistical analysis of a group numerical data. In the view of Cassell and Symon (2004), the assumption behind the positivist paradigm is that there is an objective truth existing in the world that can be measured and explained scientifically. The main concerns of the quantitative paradigm are that measurement is reliable, valid, and generalizable in its clear prediction of cause and effect.

The quantitative data collection method provides the information in the form of numbers and statistics. The objective of quantitative research is to develop and employ mathematical models, theories and/or hypothesis pertaining to phenomena. The process of measurement is central to quantitative research because it provides the fundamental connection between empirical observation and mathematical expression of quantitative relationships (Matveev, 2002).

Some of the strengths of quantitative data are that produced information is quantifiable, reliable and universal to some larger people. (Jill and Hussey, 2003), achieves high levels of reliability of gathered data due to controlled observations, laboratory experiments, mass surveys, or other form of research manipulations (Basely, 1970) and eliminates or minimizes subjectivity of judgment (Kealey and Protheroe, 1996).

3.3 STUDY DESIGN

A research study design is a set of logical procedures that enables one to obtain evidence to determine the degree to which a theoretical hypothesis is correct. In line with this, the study design for this work shall be cross-sectional because of time constraints for the research. Most importantly a cross sectional design is centered on observations made at a particular point in time such as survey research. Cross sectional study is more suited for researches that require a broader scope of data collection or more than one case or a small group which differentiates it from a case study. With cross sectional study design it is not easy to make inferences about processes that occur over a period of time and hence cause and effect (David, 2004). The generalizability of the cross sectional study is considered very good because they are a representative of given a given population.

3.4 SAMPLING METHODOLOGY

3.4.1 Population

The population selected for this study comprises of respondents from information and communication technology (ICT) companies in Cyberjaya, which has a high concentration of ICT companies. This study is limited to this population and spreads through all ranks of the practitioners of project management within the selected organizations. The population consisted of both male and female gender and the researcher tried to ensure an even distribution of the questionnaire among them. The researcher also ensured that that information was gathered across all ranks of the organization. Also there was no age restriction for the population of bracket of study.

3.4.2 Sample size

The sample selected for the purpose of this research will comprise of respondents from ICT companies in Cyberjaya, which has a high concentration of information, and communication technology (ICT) companies that embark on projects from time to time. As such data gathered from this region would be used to determine factors that cause project failure in information and communication technology (ICT) Companies. Considering the size of this population under consideration (which is considered to be very large), it would be very difficult and almost impossible to collect data from every single employee in the industry. This will not only be time consuming but also capital intensive (expensive). As such following the sample size table as proposed by Krejice and Morgan (1970) the researcher is confident that the sample is enough to derive the characteristics of the whole population through the use of statistical method in order to attain 95% confidence interval.

3.4.3 Sampling Techniques

This research uses a simple random sampling method as the sampling technique of data collection. This method can be understood as a group of individuals chosen from a large group often regard as the sample and population respectively. Each individual in the sample is randomly chosen by chance (Starnes, 2008).

3.5 DATA COLLECTION INSTRUMENTS USED

A questionnaire is utilized as the primary data instrument for the purpose of this research. These days, the popular method for collecting data is the questionnaire survey, which is cheaper, and less time consuming than conducting interviews and considering large samples. While preparing the questionnaires the researcher followed some simple rules to reduce the level of complexity and to ensure that respondents understand the various questions in the questionnaires. These steps are explained below.

- Keeping the questionnaire as simple as possible so as to avoid any form of ambiguity or misunderstanding on the part of respondents.
- Avoid misguiding respondents by explaining the purpose of the research to them
- In addition to ensuring that questions were constructed in a way that they will connote only one meaning the researcher also ensured that negative questions were avoided all through the questionnaire.
- It was also ensured that each question addressed only a single issue
- Effort was also made to avoid any form of offensive and insensitive question
- The issue of confidentiality was also addressed. Hence the research pledged to keep the information provided by respondents as such
- These researches basically rely on questionnaires as the vehicle for extracting primary research data; questions were reviewed many times in the guidance of the supervisors of this project.

3.6 STATISTICAL TOOLS USED

The data that would be collected via the distribution of questionnaires would be analyzed using SPSS (version 22) software where various tests would be carried out to determine the result of the data. The statistical package for social sciences is a widely used application/programme in the field of social sciences today. It is also used by data miners, education researchers, health researchers, market researchers, survey companies and even governments to mention but a few. As far back as the early 70s Bent and Hull in the manual of the statistical package of social sciences did describe it as the most influential book in sociology mainly because of the fact that it gave room for nonprofessional researchers to carry out their own data analysis. Apart from being used for the purpose of statistical analysis, the statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) for data management (in the form of creating derived data, file reshaping and case selection and data documentation. There is quite numbers of statistics included in the statistical package of social sciences a hand full of which is utilized in this work by the researcher. Some of these include, descriptive statistics (such as frequencies, descriptives, cross tabulation, descriptive ration tabulation and Explore); Bivariate statistics (t-test, Means, Anova, correlation and nonparametric tests); prediction for numerical outcomes (linear regression analysis); prediction for identifying groups (cluster analysis, discriminant and factor analysis) to mention but a few.

3.7 ETHICAL ISSUES

Almost every profession or discipline today has its a set of rules that guides the conduct of its members or practitioners. Further than performing the of a mere conduct guide, these standards also serve as means of aligning the activities of members with the set objectives and goals of the organization, body, institution or profession in question. The disciplines of engineering, medicine, law and business for instance for their highly regarded ethical norms.

Within the context of academic research, there are a number of reasons why it is important for researchers to consider and ensure adherence to ethical norms during their entire research. First and foremost, it is important to note that norms helps to promote the primary aims of a research which are, discovery of truth, acquisition of knowledge and the avoidance of error. This helps the researcher to avoid misconducts such as the falsification or fabrication of data, misrepresentation of research error as against the promotion of truth and minimization of error. Furthermore, the natures of some researches require the efforts of many and not just one individual. Such researches require a great deal of corporation, collaborative effort and coordination among many different people in different disciplines and institutions. In such a situation ethical standards also promote the values that are essential to collaborative work, such as trust, accountability, mutual respect, and fairness. For example, there are quite a number of ethical norms in researches that look into guidelines for sensitive issues such as confidentiality, copy right, authorship, patenting policies to mention but a few. These policies are enacted to protect intellectual property while at the same time trying to encourage some level of collaboration among scholars. It is only normal for researchers to want to receive credit and acknowledgement for their respective contributions to knowledge and of course prevent their ideas and works from being stolen and ascribed to

others. This is a major offence in the academic world. (David, 2004). In truth, quite a handful of moral and social values are promoted and encouraged by the norms in research some of which include the issue of social responsibly, keeping the law, health and human right to mention but a few. There is no doubt that the presence of ethical lapses in research work can significantly harm the end product and acceptability of the findings of the research in the academic world.

In all, ethical issues arise in almost every facet of human activities. The quest of conducting a research of this magnitude is not an exception in this regard as well since experience has shown that a lot of ethical issues arise in the process of conducting researches of this sort. With this in mind the research takes vital ethical issues into consideration before and especially during the data gathering face of the study. Firstly the researcher tied to avoid the ethical issue of plagiarism by ensuring that all borrowed ideas and materials are properly referenced. Secondly, because the information that is being gathered by this research is related to personal perceptions it was also essential to address the issue of confidentiality. Hence the researcher assured respondents that the information provided would be treated as classified and confidential within the context of this research work.

3.8 THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Framework: Adapted from Sonja Hughes (2010)

3.9 Data Collection Process

1.1 issue identifying for data collecting

The initial step is to distinguish issues as well as open doors for gathering information and to choose what next strides to take. To do this, it might be useful to direct an interior and outer appraisal to comprehend what is going on inside and outside of the association.

A few associations, as FCP and Legislated Employment Equity Plan (LEEP), are given particular heading on what issues ought to be investigated and how information must be gathered. Different associations may have more adaptability to choose when and how to gather data to accomplish certain objectives. A portion of the non-comprehensive inquiries recognized underneath may apply to a differing scope of associations and gatherings of people, including workers and administration clients. Contingent upon the association, these inquiries might be considered at Step 1, or at various stages in an information gathering process.

1.2 issue selection

The center of Step 2 is picking a need issue(s) as well as opportunity(ies) for gathering information, and afterward setting objectives and goals.

The association surveys the issues as well as circumstances recognized from the inner and outer evaluation done in Step 1, and picks at least one particular issues and additionally open doors for beginning an information accumulation extend from among the rundown of needs.

1.3 methode planing :

In Step 3, associations will settle on choices about will's identity studied, how information will be gathered, the wellsprings of information that will be utilized, and the term of the information accumulation extend, among different inquiries. These choices might be made in conference with a specialist. The techniques and methodologies will spill out of the objectives set in Step 2, and will differ essentially relying upon various variables, including the association's specific situation, size, assets, and the reason and multifaceted nature of the issue(s) or opportunity(ies) chose.

1.4 data collection

At the point when anticipating how best to gather information in Step 4, it is essential to know about the reasonable contemplations and best practices for tending to calculated difficulties associations frequently confront at this phase of the procedure. Executing an information accumulation arrange requires consideration

1.5 data anlysis

Step 5 includes dissecting and translating the information gathered. Whether quantitative and additionally subjective strategies for social affair information are utilized, the investigation can be intricate, or less in this way, contingent upon the techniques utilized and the measure of information gathered. Clarifying the specialized strides required in dissecting and translating information is past the extent of this guide. An association will need to figure out if it has the interior limit and aptitude to investigate and decipher information itself, or whether it will require the assistance of an outer expert.

A littler association that has essential information accumulation needs might have the capacity to depend on inside mastery and existing assets to decipher the significance of assembled information.

1.6 act on result

Once an association has examined and deciphered the aftereffects of the information gathered, it might choose to follow up on the information, gather business as usual sort of information or alter its approach.

Quantitative and subjective data can give a strong premise to making a viable activity arrange intended to accomplish key authoritative HR, human rights, value and differing qualities objectives recognized through the information accumulation handle.

Figure 1.3: Data analysis framework

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS

4.0 INTRODUCTION

This chapter deals with an analysis of the gathered data in this research. The data were gathered and processed with specific tools in line with the problems posed in the first chapter. More than anything else this chapter provides the basis for assessing the outlined objectives of the research namely; to find out and understand the factors that aid project success in organizations, to come up with measures to prevent and avoid project failure in organizations and to identify possible strategies that could be implemented to aid project success in organizations.

Data for this research was primarily from a questionnaire, which was adopted as the research tool. This was subdivided into two parts. The first part gathered personal information of respondents while the second part pondered on questions on the dependent and independent variables of the research.

4.1 RESPONSE RATE

In all, a total of four hundred and fifty surveys were sent to different information and communication technology (ICT) companies in Cyberjaya. Of these entire some the respondent was able to collect a total sum of 386. Of these 386 returned survey, 35 were wither not filled by respondents at all or they were partially filled (while leaving out vital portions of the survey). Consequently these surveys were exclude from the a lot resulting in the total number of 351 which was analyzed in this research.

4.2 DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF STUDY

Table 1

What is your Gender?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Male	194	55.3	55.3	55.3
	Female	157	44.7	44.7	100.0
	Total	351	100.0	100.0	

The table above shows the gender distribution of participants in the survey. While the male gender had a higher percentage of 55.3% as against the female gender with 44.7 percent the marginal difference between the two is not much. The implication of this therefore is that the survey was evenly distributed to both sexes.

Table 2

What is your age range?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	20 years old	32	9.1	9.1	9.1
	21-30	163	46.4	46.4	55.6
	31-40	105	29.9	29.9	85.5
	41 and Above	51	14.5	14.5	100.0
	Total	351	100.0	100.0	

Although the impact of age as intermediate variable is not studied in this research, the above, the above table shows the aged distribution of respondents. 32 respondents indicated they were 20 years old, 163 between the ages of 21 and 30, 105 between 31 and 40 while a minority of 51 respondents indicated they were 41 years old and above. This is an indication that more people within the ages of 21 to 30 are more likely to be drawn to a carrier in the in industry of study.

What is your Marital Status?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Single	134	38.2	38.2	38.2
	Married	107	30.5	30.5	68.7
	Divorced	71	20.2	20.2	88.9
	Widow	39	11.1	11.1	100.0
	Total	351	100.0	100.0	

Marital status of respondents was categorized under the subheads of single, married, divorced widowed. A larger percentage of respondents were either single or married while a minority indicated they were either divorced or widowed as indicated in the table above.

Table 3

What is your highest level of education?

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Diploma or Lower	84	23.9	23.9	23.9
	Bachelor degree	144	41.0	41.0	65.0
	Master's Degree	94	26.8	26.8	91.7
	PHD	9	2.6	2.6	94.3
	Other	20	5.7	5.7	100.0
	Total	351	100.0	100.0	

In a challenging industry like the industry of study, some level of educational qualification would be expected of respondents. The result of the data did not prove different as 84, respondents indicated they had diploma or lesser degrees, 144 bachelor's degree, 94 master's degree, 9 PHD and others indicated other forms of professional qualifications such project management professionals (PMP) and Certified manager (CM).

Table 4

How long have you been in this organization?					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	1 to 2 Years	79	22.5	22.5	22.5
	Less than 5 Years	152	43.3	43.3	65.8
	5 to 10 Years	96	27.4	27.4	93.2
	10 Years and Above	24	6.8	6.8	100.0
	Total	351	100.0	100.0	

The time spent in their respective organizations varied from one respondent to the other. 22.5 percent indicated they had only spent between 1 to 2 years, 43.3 percent above two years but less than five years, and 27.4 percent between 5 to 10 years while twenty-four had been with their companies for more than 10 years.

4.3 RELIABILITY

In statistics, reliability has to do with the consistency of a survey, test, observation or any form of measuring device. It is the degree to which an assessment tool produces stable and consistent result, which informs the level to which it can be relied upon. It is one of the two most important aspects of precision; the first of which is validity. Reliability can also be said to be the predictability of a measurement. It is quantified by taking several measurements on the same subjects. Poor reliability degrades the precision of a single measurement and reduces your ability to track changes in measurements or in experimental studies.

Planning

Cronbach Alphas measure internal consistency between a set or number of items. The table below shows the cronbach Alpha for the variable planning which is 0.496, which is approximately 50%. In the view of Westberg (2004), a Cronbach Alpha within this range is considered as good in a quantitative research.

Table 5a

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.496	.486	5

Table 5b

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
How long have you been in this organization?	2.24	.932	351
Proper cost estimation facilitate project success	3.91	1.271	351
Proper planning and scheduling facilitate project success	3.94	1.279	351
Planning with the project team aids project performance	3.54	1.358	351
Adequate	3.76	1.337	351

supervision impact projects positively			
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Table 5c

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
How long have you been in this organization?	15.16	11.161	.131	.027	.511
Proper cost estimation facilitate project success	13.48	8.639	.347	.221	.386
Proper planning and scheduling facilitate project success	13.46	8.660	.339	.221	.392
Plannig with the project team aids project performance	13.85	8.755	.280	.136	.434
Adequate supervision impact projects positively	13.64	9.072	.246	.122	.457

Clear Goals

Cronbach Alphas measure internal consistency between a set or number of items. The table below shows the cronbach Alpha for the variable clear goal which is 0.534. In the view of Westberg (2004), a Cronbach Alpha within this range is considered as good in a quantitative research.

Table 6a

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.534	.689	5

Table 6b

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Setting realistic expectations help achieve project success	4.11	1.222	351
Project activities are aligned with project goals and objectives	4.81	.389	351
Clear vision and strategy facilitates project management performance	4.83	.377	351
Project managers	4.70	.493	351

offer adequate explanations in relation to project goals whenever the need arises			
Project manages implement clear strategies in my organizations	4.64	.480	351

Table 6c

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Setting realistic expectations help achieve project success	18.99	1.628	.265	.090	.705
Project activities are aligned with project goals and objectives	18.28	3.176	.447	.295	.448
Clear vision and strategy facilitates project management performance	18.27	3.198	.450	.368	.450
Project managers offer adequate explanations in relation to project goals whenever the need arises	18.40	2.937	.453	.431	.417
Project manages implement clear strategies in my organizations	18.46	3.163	.324	.228	.478

Project Scope

Cronbach Alphas measure internal consistency between a set or number of items. The table below shows the cronbach Alpha for the variable project scope which is 0.649. In the view of Westberg (2004), a Cronbach Alpha within this range is considered as good in a quantitative research.

Table 7a

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.649	.654	5

Table 7b

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Clear project scope is important for project management success	4.55	.762	351
Adequate training and development is important for project success	4.58	.796	351
The project scope is made clear to all stakeholders and team members	4.49	.759	351

The roles of every project team member in alignment with the project scope is made clear	4.56	.853	351
The manager tries to avoid any major change in scope	4.51	.636	351

Table 7c

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Clear project scope is important for project management success	18.14	4.227	.406	.231	.595
Adequate training and development is important for project success	18.11	4.034	.442	.284	.577
The project scope is made clear to all stakeholders and team members	18.19	3.894	.537	.396	.530
The roles of every project team member in alignment with the project scope is made clear	18.13	4.339	.285	.120	.659
The manager tries to avoid any major change in scope	18.17	4.668	.366	.156	.614

Effective Communication

Cronbach Alphas measure internal consistency between a set or number of items. The table below shows the cronbach Alpha for the variable effective communication which is 0.518. In the view of Westberg (2004), a Cronbach Alpha within this range is considered as good in a quantitative research

Table 8a

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.518	.541	5

Table 8b

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Communication is done from time to time within the team	4.66	.547	351
There are clear and reliable communication channels within my organization	4.63	.778	351
Feedback is encouraged and treated with urgency	4.77	.531	351
Project managers are accessible to the	4.66	.685	351

project team and stake holders at all times			
Project managers make communicate in clear and concise manner.	4.83	.372	351

Table 8c

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Communication is done from time to time within the team	18.89	2.375	.232	.122	.494
There are clear and reliable communication channels within my organization	18.93	1.869	.278	.205	.485
Feedback is encouraged and treated with urgency	18.79	2.058	.475	.323	.354
Project managers are accessible to the project team and stake holders at all times	18.89	2.051	.277	.157	.472
Project managers make communicate in clear and concise manner.	18.72	2.636	.240	.178	.496

Project Management Success

Cronbach Alphas measure internal consistency between a set or number of items. The table below shows the cronbach Alpha for the variable project management success which is 0.649. In the view of Westberg (2004), a Cronbach Alpha within this range is considered as good in a quantitative research.

Table 9a

Reliability Statistics		
Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.644	.646	5

Table 9b

Item Statistics			
	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Effective communication among team members and with stakeholders leads to project management success	3.93	1.269	351
Effective change management leads to project success	3.96	1.274	351
Effective man Management results in project success	3.58	1.365	351

Project manager knowledge and skills is very important to project success	3.80	1.342	351
Availability of appropriate technological impact project success positively	4.01	1.212	351

Table 9c

Item-Total Statistics					
	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Squared Multiple Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
Effective communication among team members and with stake holders leads to project management success	15.34	12.528	.348	.236	.614
Effective change management leads to project success	15.31	12.849	.305	.212	.634
Effective man Management results in project success	15.69	11.916	.369	.163	.606
Project manager knowledge and skills is very important to project success	15.47	11.318	.459	.431	.560
Availability of appropriate technological impact project success positively	15.26	11.531	.518	.426	.536

4.4 REGRESSION ANALYSIS

LINEAR REGRESSIONS AMONG VARIABLES

Planning and Project management success.

The table below shows the value of R, which is the relationship; the value of R square which predicts the variance and the adjusted R Square which states the best value of the R square which can fit into the model. The value of the adjusted R square predicts the variance between the dependent and independent variable; in this case, the value of the adjusted R square implies that 48.1% of variance is predicted by the variable planning over project management success.

Table 10

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.695 ^a	.482	.481	.59862	.482	325.307	1	349	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), PLANNING									

Clear Goals and Project management success.

The value of the adjusted R Square predicts the variance between the dependent and independent variable. Here, the value of the adjusted R square implies that 44.3 % of variance is predicted by the clear goals over project management success.

Table 11

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.667 ^a	.445	.443	.62002	.445	279.563	1	349	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), GOALS									

Project Scope and Project management success.

The value of the adjusted R Square predicts the variance between the dependent and independent variable. Here, the value of the adjusted R square implies that 65.7 % of variance is predicted by the project scope over project management success

Table 12

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.811 ^a	.658	.657	.48682	.658	670.589	1	349	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), SCOPE									

Communication and Project management success.

The table below shows the value of R, which is the relationship, the value of R square which predicts the variance and the adjusted R square which states the best value of the R square which can fit into the model. The value of the adjusted R square predicts the variance between the dependent and independent variable; in this case, the value of the adjusted R square implies that 57.0 % of variance is predicted by the variable communication over project management success.

Table 13

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.755 ^a	.570	.569	.54536	.570	463.430	1	349	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), COMMUNICATION									

CORRELATION BETWEEN THE DEPENDENT AND INDEPENDENT VARIABLES

Correlation is a factual estimation of the relationship between two factors to such an extent that is a variety in one is connected with variety in the other (Babbie 2010). It is a solitary number that depicts the level of relationship between two factors (William 2006). The factors are not allotted as free or ward. Connection is utilized as a part of measuring the quality and bearing of the current relationship between the factors. It fluctuates from - 1 and 1. The relationship could be either positive or negative with a positive relationship going from 0 to 1 and a negative relationship going from 0 to - 1. The further the esteem is far from 0, the more grounded the relationship. The assessed measure for quality is 0 for no impact, .1 shows a little impact, .3 demonstrates a medium impact, and .5 shows an expansive impact (Jacob et al. 2002).

The Pearson relationship examination of the table has demonstrated incredible quality among the factors. Every one of the factors have a relationship of more than 60 % which implies that the quality of the relationship is running from direct to solid among the factors tried for this examination.

Correlation measure relationship between two or more variables with the aid of the variation they associate with one another (Babbie, 2010). It is in important to note that in correlations the variables are not essentially designated as dependent or independent. It shows the strength and level of an existing relationship between variables. The relationship is usually measured between the range of -1 to 1 with -1 showing a negative relationship and 1 showing a the highest and very strong level of relationship.

Based on the Pearson correlation analysis table shown below all variables show very strong relationship that is well above 60 percent which is a clear indication of strong relationship between the variables of this research.

Table 14

Correlations						
		SUCCE SS	PLANNI NG	GOAL S	SCOP E	COMMUN ICATION
Pearson Correlation	SUCCESS	1.000	.695	.667	.811	.755
	PLANNING	.695	1.000	.543	.596	.568
	GOALS	.667	.543	1.000	.600	.624
	SCOPE	.811	.596	.600	1.000	.666
	COMMUNICA TION	.755	.568	.624	.666	1.000
Sig. (1-tailed)	SUCCESS	.	.000	.000	.000	.000
	PLANNING	.000	.	.000	.000	.000
	GOALS	.000	.000	.	.000	.000
	SCOPE	.000	.000	.000	.	.000
	COMMUNICA TION	.000	.000	.000	.000	.
N	SUCCESS	351	351	351	351	351
	PLANNING	351	351	351	351	351
	GOALS	351	351	351	351	351
	SCOPE	351	351	351	351	351
	COMMUNICA TION	351	351	351	351	351

Based on the correlation table above the predicted hypothesis in stated below are either rejected or accepted as indicted below.

HO: There is no relationship between project success and clear goals and objectives (Rejected)

H1: There is a positive relationship between project success and clear goals and objectives (Accepted)

HO: There is no relationship between project success and clear goals and objectives (Rejected)

H2 There is a positive relationship between project success and planning. (Accepted)

HO: There is no relationship between project success and clear project scope (Rejected)

H3: There is a positive relationship between project success and clear project scope (Accepted)

H0: There is no relationship between project success and effective communication (rejected)

H4: There is a positive relationship between project success and effective communication (Accepted)

MULTIPLE REGRESSIONS

Table 15

Model Summary									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.886 ^a	.784	.782	.38796	.784	314.854	4	346	.000
a. Predictors: (Constant), COMMUNICATION, PLANNING, GOALS, SCOPE									

Table 16

ANOVA ^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	189.556	4	47.389	314.854	.000 ^b
	Residual	52.077	346	.151		
	Total	241.633	350			
a. Dependent Variable: SUCCESS						
b. Predictors: (Constant), COMMUNICATION, PLANNING, GOALS, SCOPE						

Table 17

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.254	.105		2.418	.016
	PLANNING	.210	.031	.221	6.663	.000
	GOALS	.111	.031	.124	3.603	.000
	SCOPE	.410	.035	.426	11.569	.000
	COMMUNICATION	.238	.033	.269	7.291	.000

Table 18

Coefficient Correlations ^a						
Model			COMMUNICATI ON	PLANNI NG	GOAL S	SCOP E
1	Correlatio ns	COMMUNIC ATION	1.000	-.200	-.320	-.380
		PLANNING	-.200	1.000	-.204	-.288
		GOALS	-.320	-.204	1.000	-.238
		SCOPE	-.380	-.288	-.238	1.000
	Covarianc es	COMMUNIC ATION	.001	.000	.000	.000
		PLANNING	.000	.001	.000	.000
		GOALS	.000	.000	.001	.000
		SCOPE	.000	.000	.000	.001

a. Dependent Variable: SUCCESS

Table 19

Collinearity Diagnostics ^a								
Mo del	Dimens ion	Eigenva lue	Condition Index	Variance Proportions				
				(Consta nt)	PLAN NING	GOAL S	SCOP E	COMMUNICATIO N
1	1	4.900	1.000	.00	.00	.00	.00	.00
	2	.034	11.963	.71	.02	.16	.01	.14
	3	.025	14.072	.13	.30	.69	.06	.08
	4	.023	14.667	.12	.61	.15	.04	.37
	5	.018	16.617	.03	.07	.00	.89	.41

a. Dependent Variable: SUCCESS

The multiple regressions table above shows more about the relationship between all the independent variables and the dependent variable. It also shows the relative contribution of each of the predictors to the total variance.

CHAPTER FIVE

5.0 INTRODUCTION

As the last chapter of this research, the follows from the succeeding four chapters by embarking on a re-examination the objectives and goals outlined at the beginning of the research. Consequently, here the researcher took a look at the findings and results of the analysis, the implications of the research as well a conclusion and recommendation possible research areas that could be explored in the nearest future within the subject of focus.

5.1 DISCUSSIONS

Irrespective of their different sizes, nearly all projects are managed in a systematic pattern today owing to the rise and acceptance of project management as an effective means achieving deliverables. Despite this, it is also a fact that while some projects have been successful, some other still fail. This research work examines 'why projects should not fail' by examining the factors that affect project management success. In summary, all hypotheses were confirmed apart from the null hypotheses.

5.1.1 Planning

The first hypothesis predicted that planning had a positive impact on project management success. Based on the analysis of the data collected from the survey the correlation analysis indicated a strong and significant relationship between planning and project management success. In truth, the importance of project planning in any project management endeavor cannot be pushed to the limits. This is because planning serves as the foundation, which the execution of a project is based. Project management is just like an edifice such that without a stable and strong foundation the entire project structure has a strong likelihood of collapsing. According to Tracey

(2015) apart from the stability that proper planning gives a project, it also helps to avoid and eliminate wastage as it applies to allocated resources for the execution of the project. Strongly tied to the concept of planning is cost estimation. The significance of cost estimation (which an aspect of planning) in project management has been attested by scholars (PMI, 2009 and Ricardo 2008) who affirmed that accurate estimation of cost and resources during the planning process can go a long way to impact the positive outcome of the project. As such, the planning phase, cost estimation should be given adequate attention. The management of organizations must also ensure that project managers are well trained and equipped with the necessary tools and skills to make accurate cost estimation and planning so as to ensure the attainment of project deliverables and by implication achieve project success.

5.1.2 Clear Goals

In the view of Michael (2004), one of the most common mistakes in the field of project management is inadequate definition, which is a synonym for clear goals. The second hypothesis of this research predicted a positive relationship between clear goals and project management success. In harmony with earlier researches, this hypothesis was also confirmed as indicated in the Pearson correlation analysis. Embarking on a project without a clear goals and objectives could be best described as starting out on a journey without an idea of where you are going to or when you will get there. In other words for any project management endeavor to be successful there is need for the project manager or organization must place more emphasis on ensuring that every team member or employee knows what he or she is expected to accomplish both in the present and in the future. When the goals of the project are clear to team members or employees it becomes easier for them to contribute to the greater good (Feliciano, 2015). This also makes

the job of the project manager easier since project team members or employees already have a clear understanding to the goals, what is expected on them and how to proceed to achieve these goals in harmony with the project scope.

5.1.3 Project Scope

H3 in this research predicted a positive relationship between project scope and project management success. In other words, when the scope of a project is properly managed (taking the factor of change into consideration), there is a greater chance for a project to be successful. The above-mentioned hypothesis was confirmed by the research implying that for a project not to fail, proper scope management is a necessary condition for project managers and other project stakeholders. Effective scope management is essential for project management success. In order to achieve effective project scope management therefore, managers and organizations must ensure that there is clear and good communication since this will ensure that project team members have a clear understanding of the project scope and work towards how the project goal will be met (Monnappa, 2012). Furthermore, project scope helps to avoid (Such as bloating scope and unruly requirements) that projects run the risk of facing by setting out what is and what is not included in the project and also controls what gets to be added or removed as the project is implemented. Furthermore, without a clear definition of the project scope it will be difficult to estimate the cost or time that would be needed for the project. Scope change at any level directly affects project cost and time (Carsidy, 2014).

5.1.4 Effective Communication

The fourth hypothesis (H4), also predicts a positive relationship between effective communication and project management success. This hypothesis was confirmed in this research and the null hypothesis, which states that there is no positive relationship between effective communication and project management success, was not confirmed and as such will be rejected. This finding is in harmony with early research such as Dutta (2015) who opined that the effective communication with both internal and external stakeholders is vital to the attainment of project success in any organization. The finding of this research is further alluded to when at the nature of the project team in our business world today. Most project teams today comprise of a diverse group of individuals. Hence, it is not just important that the project manager must ensure

Effective communication with the project team as whole, it is more important that there is effective communication within the team as well.

It is not just enough to know what to do, it is more important to select the right channel to implement it. In other words, project managers must carefully select the right channel and methods to communicate with all stakeholders and with the project team. The manager must ensure that vital aspects of the project such as panning the scope, the time and cost of the project are clearly communicated to all stakeholders and failure to do this can affect the project negatively in a variety of ways. In the view of Dutta (2015) most of the projects that fail in our business world today can be traced to some flaws in effective communication at one stage or the other during the planning or execution of the project.

5.2 RESEARCH IMPLICATIONS AND RECOMMENDATION

The implication of this research is two-dimensional. On the one hand, this research has implication on the specific industry of study namely ICT companies in Cyberjaya Malaysia since the data utilized in this research was primarily gathered from this population. On the other hand, the finding of this research has implication for all organizations in general by inference. While the findings of this research may not be enforced on all organizations however, it is important to point out the fact that they can still be used for the purpose of improvement of project management processes in organizations both within and outside the industry of study.

Four independent variables laid bare and examined in this research with each of them predicting a positive relationship with the dependent variable (project management success). In all, all for hypotheses are confirmed and accepted indicating that the selected variables can lead to project management success at different levels if well implemented and managed in the project management process. Consequently, it becomes very necessary for project managers in particular and ICT companies at large to pay attention to these factors to ensure the execution of projects from the start to finish and ensure the achievements of organizational set goals and objectives.

Furthermore, this research showed varying levels of relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. It is important to note that this does not in any way imply or assert the superiority of any of the independent variables over the others. On the contrary, it could be said that all variables exert the same level of importance in the sense that they are capable of aiding project success. These variables should therefore be treated as a whole and implemented as such so as yield a more satisfying result. It is also important that organizations become very courteous in educating its project managers and putting procedures in place to ensure that the all

the potentials incumbent in these factors are well explored and implement to the possible pit falls that could be brought about by these factors are avoided. It is also important that project managers are trained to possess management techniques since they are the foundation for running projects. Management techniques set the processes and procedures required to measure progress. It is true that we do not live in a perfect world, however, these simple set of techniques help set the stage for handling troubled projects and minimizes their impact. Hence project managers must also be incorporate leadership skills with their management skills.

5.3 CONCLUSION

Just as there are, many examples of failed projects so also are many more examples of project that have been successful in our business world today. This is an indication that project failure can be avoided or prevented with good planning, clarifications of goals, proper project scope implementation and effective communication. On the other hand, once a project starts to fail, there are techniques to recognize it, minimize the extent of the project failure and make the project recovery as successful as possible. There may be some casualties along the way, such as some reduction in scope, additional time, and/or additional cost, but with good project planning and timely intervention where required, these can be minimized. In other for the above to be possible, it is important for organizations to invest in their project managers by ensuring that they are well groomed and trained. A project manager needs to be trained in the techniques of not just recovering failing project, but more importantly, reducing the chances of creating one themselves in the future.

In conclusion, the panacea to the problem of project failure is not a single tool, process or strategy. On the contrary, it is a combination of people, processes and tools. Good processes should be implemented that are customized for the business. Executive management must show leadership by spending the time it takes to plan, set goals and strategies, prior to embarking on projects. It is also important that project managers are courageous enough to voice out whenever the expectations of stakeholders are unrealistic. Failure to do this can lead to project failure even before the project begins.

5.4 LIMITATION OF STUDY

This research focuses on an examination of the factors that aid success with special focus on ICT companies in Cyberjaya. Due to the fact that researchers in this area of study have done less work, it was quite challenging to gather secondary data based on the limitation of ready-made academic materials on the subject of study. Furthermore, the number of ICT companies in Cyberjaya also makes it impossible to collect data from every single project manager in the industry. Because of this, only a sample of the entire population is considered from the specified location of study. With the use of statistical techniques, the sample is enough to derive the characteristics of the entire population.

5.5 SUGGESTION FOR FUTURE RESEARCH

The findings of this research can be said to be subjective in the sense that it focuses on a particular industry within a selected locality or environment namely, the information and communication industry (ICT) in Cyberjaya, Malaysia. Because of this future research can still be carried out in other industries such as the service industry and other industries that have a large presence of project management activities and professionals. Also, the quantitative approach was chosen as the methodology for this research while using a survey method as the primary method of data collection. Future research can also done by exploring the use of interviews or a combination of the two so as to be able to come up with more comprehensive findings.

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APPENDIX A

Questionnaire

Dear sir/madam,

I am Fatima... an **MBA** student of Limkokwing University of Creative Technology. This questionnaire is designed to examine “why projects should not fail. An examination of critical success factors in project management”. The failure of projects is no longer alien to our business world today. This survey helps to identify factors that cause project failure. This study will not only help to identify those factors that cause project failure but most importantly it lays the foundation to avoiding the pit falls of project failure while at the same time assuring the project success. I will really appreciate if you could spare a few minutes to fill up this questionnaire, as it is a crucial part to the completion of MBA program. Note: **All your answers shall be treated with utmost confidentiality.**

Part A: Background information

This section refers to the background information, please go through and provide the appropriate information for each question.

What is your Gender?

- Male
- Female

What is your age range?

- Less than 25 years old
- 26 – 35 years old
- 36 – 45 years old
- 46 – 55 years old

- 56 years and above

What is your Marital Status?

- Single
- Married
- Divorced
- Widow

What is your highest level of education?

- Diploma or lower
- Bachelor's Degree
- Master's Degree
- PHD
- Others

How long have you been in this organization?

- 1 to 2 Years
- Less than 5 years
- 5 to 10 Years
- 10 years and above

PART B

Planning	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Neither disagree nor agree	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree
Proper cost estimation facilitate project success					
Proper planning and Scheduling facilitate project success					
Planning with the project team aids project performance					
Adequate supervision impact project positively					
The availability of the complete requirements to execute a project helps facilitate project success					

Clear Goals	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Neither disagree nor agree	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree
Setting realistic expectations help achieve project success					
Project activities are aligned with project goals and objectives					
Clear vision and strategy facilitates project management performance					
Project managers offer adequate explanations in relation to project goals whenever the need arises					
Project manages implement clear strategies in my organizations					

Project Scope	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Neither disagree nor agree	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree
Clear project scope is important for project management success					
Adequate training and development is important for project success					
The project scope is made clear to all stakeholders and team members					
The roles of every project team member in alignment with the project scope is made clear					
The manager tries to avoid any major change in scope					

Effective communication	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Neither disagree nor agree	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree
Communication is done from time to time within the team					
There are clear and reliable communication channels within my organization					
Feedback is encouraged and treated with urgency					
Project managers are accessible to the project team and stake holders at all times					
Project managers make communicate in clear and concise manner.					

Project Management Success	1. Strongly Disagree	2. Disagree	3. Neither disagree nor agree	4. Agree	5. Strongly Agree
Effective communication among team members and with stake holders leads to project management success					
Effective change management leads to project success					
Effective man Management results in project success					
Project manager knowledge and skills is very important to project success					
Availability of appropriate technological impact project success positively					

Thanks!

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

ICT	Information and communication technology
SPSS	Statistical data for social sciences
PM	Project Manager
IV	Independent variable
DV	Independent Variable
PMBOK	Project Management Body of Knowledge
PMIS	Project Management Information System
PMO	Program Management Office